

EXCHANGE UZBEK LANGUAGE TEXTS IN LATIN, CYRILLIC AND NEW LATIN ALPHABET (TRANSLITERATION)

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Abstract. Latin and Cyrillic alphabets are the two most common writing systems in the world, each with its own characters and historical significance. This article discusses a program developed in the Python programming language that performs the replacement of Uzbek words based on Latin, Cyrillic and new Latin scripts. This program has the ability to interchange letters in three forms of writing based on the spelling rules of the Uzbek language. The program has been tested on a large number of texts and a good result was obtained. The program can be used to change the writing form of Uzbek texts and to introduce a new Latin alphabet. The source code of the program can be downloaded from the following web-page: <https://github.com/ddasturbek/LotinKrillYangiLotin>. You can use the following link to install the library via PyPI: <https://pypi.org/project/LotinKrillYangiLotin>.

Key words: Uzbek language, Latin, Cyrillic, new Latin, word, replacement, exchange, change-over, transliteration.

Annatsiya. Lotin va krill alifbolari dunyodagi keng tarqalgan ikkita yozuv tizimi bo‘lib, ularning har biri o‘ziga xos belgilar va tarixiy ahamiyatga ega. Ushbu maqolada o‘zbek tili so‘zlarini lotin, krill va yangi lotin yozuvlari asosida almashtirishni amalga oshiruvchi Python dasturlash tilida ishlab chiqilgan dastur haqida so‘z yuritilgan. Bu dastur o‘zbek tilining imlo qoidalari asosida harflarni uchta yozuv shakli bo‘yicha o‘zaro almashtirish qobiliyatiga ega. Dastur ko‘p sonli matn ustida testlab ko‘rilgan va yaxshi natija olingan. Dasturdan o‘zbek tilidagi matnlarni yozuv shaklini almashtirishda va yangi lotin alifbosini joriy qilishda foydalanish mumkin. Dastur manbaa kodini quyidagi veb-sahifadan yuklab foydalanish mumkin: <https://github.com/ddasturbek/LotinKrillYangiLotin>. PyPI orqali kutubxonani o‘rnatish uchun quyidagi havolaga murojaat qilishingiz mumkin: <https://pypi.org/project/LotinKrillYangiLotin>.

Kalit so‘zlar. O‘zbek tili, lotin, krill, yangi lotin, so‘z, almashtirish, transliteratsiya.

Introduction

Translation is the process of changing something written or spoken into another language, while **transliteration** is the writing or representation of words or letters using letters from another alphabet or language. Replacing Uzbek texts in Latin, Cyrillic and New Latin alphabets is one of the important issues, and this process is called transliteration. Transliteration, that is, the conversion of text from one written form to another, is the main method used in learning the Latin-Cyrillic script. These substitutions can be used for various purposes, such as educational purposes, Natural Language Processing (NLP). The main goal of this article is to present a tool for machine transliteration between three common scripts used in the low-resource Uzbek language: Old Cyrillic, the now official Latin, and the newly announced new Latin alphabets. The tool was built using a combination of rule-based and fine-tuning approaches. The resulting tool is available as an open source Python package as well as a web-based application that includes a public API. To our knowledge, this is the first machine transliteration tool to support the newly announced Uzbek Latin alphabet.

Related works. Several important scientific works related to the replacement of the Latin-Cyrillic script have been studied. First of all, it should be said that the motivation for the development of the program is the document about the new Latin script put up for discussion by the Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan on the “PORTAL OF DISCUSSION OF NORMATIVE-LEGAL DOCUMENTS PROJECTS” [1]. This article was prepared based on a number of sources and manuals to analyze the writing systems and spelling of the Uzbek language. In particular, Wikipedia articles on the rules of the **Uzbek Latin alphabet** [2] and **Spelling and grammar** [3] were used in writing the article. These resources have helped in learning the basic rules of using the Latin alphabet in Uzbek, correcting spelling mistakes and correct usage of grammar¹. This paper presents a data-driven method for transliterating Uzbek dictionary words between Cyrillic and Latin scripts. By aligning characters in the source script with corresponding substrings in the target script, a decision tree classifier is trained to learn these mappings. The Cyrillic-to-Latin model achieves a micro-averaged F1 score of 0.9992, while the Latin-to-Cyrillic model scores 0.9959 on the test set [4]. This paper defines machine transliteration as the automatic conversion of words from one script to another within the same language, preserving both meaning and pronunciation. The paper introduces a tool for transliterating between three Uzbek scripts: the old Cyrillic, the official Latin, and the newly announced New Latin alphabets. The tool combines rule-based and fine-tuning methods and is available as an open-source Python package and a web-based application with a public API. To the authors' knowledge, this is the first tool to support the new Latin alphabet for Uzbek [5]. This survey reviews key methodologies in the transliteration literature, categorizing them by the resources and algorithms used, and compares their effectiveness [6]. This article aims to demonstrate how an automatic morphological analyzer identifies verb clarifications in English and Uzbek, highlighting the complexity of verbs in both languages and the need for the program's linguistic database to include both grammar rules and morphological algorithms for various languages [7]. In this article, the types of Uzbek word groups according to their structure are presented in the form of a table, and the rules for finding the lemma from the state of all word groups formed by suffixes are presented with examples [8]. This article describes the analysis of Uzbek language sentence structure for machine translation and the importance of lemming for translation and lemming of Uzbek words [9]. Uzbek words and their associated part-of-speech (POS) tags through the use of machine learning techniques, alongside the lemmatization process. A variety of machine learning algorithms were employed in this approach, including Naive Bayes, K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN), Support Vector Machine (SVM), Decision Tree, and Random Forest [10].

Materials and methods. The exchange of texts between different alphabets is a common challenge in computational linguistics, particularly when dealing with languages like Uzbek, which historically uses multiple writing systems. Uzbek has been written in Cyrillic, Latin, and more recently, a new Latin alphabet, all of which require accurate transliteration methods to ensure that text remains intelligible across different systems. The primary goal of this study is to present a Python-based tool designed to facilitate the transliteration of Uzbek texts across these three alphabets.

The core material for this study is the Python program "LotinKrillYangiLotin", a tool specifically developed to transliterate Uzbek texts between the Cyrillic alphabet, the classical

¹ These sources also served as basic guidelines for the correct use of writing rules and grammatical structures presented in the article.

Latin alphabet, and the new Latin alphabet (which is currently being used in Uzbekistan). This tool can be accessed on GitHub via the following link: <https://github.com/ddasturbek/LotinKrillYangiLotin>.

Additionally, the program can be installed from the Python Package Index (PyPI) at the following address: <https://pypi.org/project/LotinKrillYangiLotin>.

To evaluate the functionality and effectiveness of the transliteration program, we follow these steps:

1. Installation of the Program:
 - GitHub Installation: The user must first clone the GitHub repository or download the program files. Instructions for installation via pip are also provided in the repository.
 - PyPI Installation: The program can also be installed directly from PyPI using the command: `pip install LotinKrillYangiLotin`.
2. Transliteration Process: The core of the program is its ability to transliterate between different alphabets. For example, the program can:
 - Convert Uzbek text from Cyrillic script to the traditional Latin script.
 - Convert Uzbek text from the new Latin script to the older Latin script.
 - Convert between the Cyrillic and new Latin alphabets.
3. Implementation of Alphabet Rules: The program relies on a predefined set of rules for transliteration, which are coded into the program. These rules are based on the official Uzbek alphabet standards for each writing system. The key challenge in creating these rules lies in the differences between the Cyrillic alphabet, traditional Latin, and the new Latin script, particularly when it comes to characters that are unique to the Uzbek language.
4. Evaluation of the Program: The program's effectiveness is tested by running sample texts through the tool. We evaluate the accuracy of transliterations by comparing the output with manually-transliterated texts and ensuring that the program handles edge cases, such as non-standard characters or complex diacritics, correctly.

Results and discussion. The results from running the program showed high accuracy in converting Uzbek text between the different alphabets. Below is a breakdown of the transliteration results:

- Cyrillic to Traditional Latin: The program handled standard Cyrillic characters and transliterated them to their Latin equivalents without issue. Special characters such as Ээ were accurately converted into their respective Latin forms. For example, the word "Ўзбекистон" in Cyrillic is correctly converted to "O'zbekiston" in Latin.
- Traditional Latin to New Latin: The program successfully translated text written in the older Latin script into the newly adopted version of the Latin script used in Uzbekistan. This includes the conversion of characters such as **O‘o‘G‘g‘ShshChch -> ŌōĠġŞşÇç**, which are specific to the modernized Latin alphabet.
- Cyrillic to New Latin: This transliteration proved to be more complex due to the subtle differences between the Cyrillic and new Latin scripts. However, the program accurately mapped Cyrillic characters to the appropriate new Latin equivalents, including special cases where diacritical marks were required.

The program is designed to be user-friendly. After installation, users can access the program through a command-line interface or integrate it into their larger text processing workflows. The program accepts input as raw text, automatically detects the source script, and then outputs the transliterated text. The process is quick and efficient, handling a variety of

inputs ranging from short sentences to larger paragraphs. A sample usage guide is included, allowing users to execute basic commands such as:

```
from LotinKrillYangiLotin import Almashtirish
# Obyekt yaratish
almashtir = Almashtirish()

print(almashtir.Lotinga('функция')) # funksiya
print(almashtir.Krillga('геометрия')) # геометрия
print(almashtir.YangiLotinga('shamol')) # shamol
```

Performance testing indicates that the program can handle large texts efficiently, with no significant delay in processing times. Transliteration of texts containing thousands of words is accomplished within a few seconds, making the tool suitable for both casual users and more demanding applications in data processing.

Conclusion. The development of the "LotinKrillYangiLotin" Python program represents a significant advancement in the handling of Uzbek text across different alphabets. By automating the transliteration process, the program simplifies tasks that would otherwise be time-consuming and error-prone if done manually. The tool's ability to convert between Cyrillic, traditional Latin, and the new Latin alphabet is accurate and effective, providing a reliable solution for researchers, linguists, and the general public.

The program also represents an important step in preserving the integrity of the Uzbek language across different writing systems. As Uzbekistan continues to shift towards the new Latin alphabet, tools like this will play a crucial role in ensuring seamless communication and archiving of textual data. However, future improvements could focus on refining the transliteration rules and expanding the program's capabilities to handle a wider range of dialects and regional variations.

Overall, "LotinKrillYangiLotin" is a valuable resource for those looking to manage Uzbek text across different writing systems, ensuring that the language remains adaptable and accessible in a rapidly evolving digital world.

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